

THERMAL TRANSPORT IN CARBON FIBRE-COPPER AND CARBON
FIBRE/ALUMINIUM COMPOSITES

Roy Taylor and Y. Qunsheng
Materials Science Centre, Manchester, U.K.
I.G. Greenfield, Centre for Composite Materials,
University of Delaware, U.S.A.

ABSTRACT

Thermal diffusivities were measured from 100–500°C for carbon fibre/aluminium matrix specimens and from 100–700°C for carbon fibre copper matrix specimens. The specimens were fabricated by vacuum hot pressing of a blended aggregate of short (H.M.) graphite fibres mixed with the metal powder. Specimens studied contained fibre volume fractions in the range 0.1–0.5 of orientations parallel and perpendicular to the pressing direction. Densities were measured and metallographic examination carried out on all samples. Thermal diffusivity of fibres was also measured.

Results showed the diffusivity to decrease with increasing volume fraction of the fibres and differences were detected between the two specimen orientations. Most significant differences were noted for the high fibre volume fractions. Higher porosity levels were noted in the higher fibre volume fraction specimens and also significantly higher levels of porosity were noted for the aluminium matrix specimens. The data are converted to thermal conductivity and discussed in the light of current theories.

KEYWORDS: Composites, carbon/copper, carbon/aluminium thermal diffusivity, thermal conductivity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Graphite fibres possess not only high strength, high modulus and low density, but, in the case of high modulus fibres possess a high thermal conductivity (1,2). The incorporation of carbon fibres into metal matrices to improve mechanical properties is of considerable interest. In contrast the thermal properties of metal matrix composites have received relatively little attention even though thermal conductivity and thermal expansivity are important in determining the thermal shock resistance. The significance of thermal conductivity for metal matrix composites in various potential applications has already been noted (3,4). Although measurements have been made on the thermal conductivity of polymer composites, (5,6) carbon/carbon (7) and ceramic composites (8,9) there have been relatively few investigations of the thermal conductivity of metal matrix composites (10,11).

In the present paper, results are reported of measurements of thermal diffusivity made on a series of composites comprising graphite fibres in matrices of copper or aluminium. High modulus short graphite fibres having L/D ratios in the range 30–100 were used. A series of composites having nominally 0.1–0.5 volume fraction of fibres were prepared by conventional hot pressing techniques. The thermal diffusivity was measured using the laser flash technique (12). Carbon fibre/copper composites were measured over the temperature range 100–700°C in orientations parallel and perpendicular to the pressing direction. The aluminium/carbon fibre composites were measured over the temperature range 100–500°C

perpendicular to the pressing direction. Microstructural characterisation of the composites was performed.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1. Composite Fabrication

Small particle-size copper and aluminium powders were selected for the metal matrices because their average diameters are approximately the same as the average diameter of the graphite filaments. This combination results in appropriate homogeneous mixtures. Hence, after weighing the desired portions of short fibres and metal powder, the aggregate was tumbled in a rotating cylindrical container for at least two hours to insure homogeneity. Since one purpose of these experiments was to investigate thermal conductivity of the composites, impurities were minimized, and consequently, no other materials were added to enhance the mixing process or improve the quality of the interface.

Pure materials listed in Table 1 were selected for composites of either graphite/aluminium or graphite/copper.

TABLE 1: MATERIALS USED FOR SPECIMENS

MATERIAL	TRADE NAME	SHAPE
Copper	ALCAN 301 (plasma arc type)	Powder (about 10 μm)
Aluminium	ALCAN 201 (plasma arc type)	Powder (about 10 μm)
Graphite	DuPont E 120	Chopped fibre (average dia. 9.2 μm)

Portions of the resulting mixtures were vacuum hot pressed into two-inch diameter cylindrical billets. To provide adequate plastic flow at the pressures applied when forming the compacts containing congruently melting metals, hot pressing was conducted near the melting temperatures of the metals in bulk graphite dies. For the copper matrix specimens, the compaction was carried out at 1050°C at 34 MPa; for the aluminium matrix specimens the conditions were 630°C at 34 MPa.

Compaction of the loose, mixed powder metals and the short graphite fibres into cylindrical billets alters the random array of fibres because of rotation of fibres away from the compaction axis. If the influence of friction of the die wall (13), stretching effects on the fibre (14,15) breaking of the fibres, interaction between fibres and rigid rotation of clumps

Fig. 1. Orientation distribution of fibres after compaction of a P-M mixture.

of fibres are not considered, a reorientation due to fibre rotation in a compressible material (16) is expected. The random angular distribution in the as-blended powders is altered by unidirectional compaction so that fibres rotate away from the compression axis. See Figure 1. Starting with the density of the blended mixture of fibres and meal powder, the compaction to virtually 100% solid density is found to be after a reduction of height of the cylindrical compact of 30% to 40%. Following this degree of densification, an elementary model (16) predicts that no fibres remain within 45° to 50° of the compaction axis. The compact is isotropic in the radial (transverse) direction; however, viewed in the longitudinal direction, there is a different angular distribution of fibres. The distinct fibre arrangements in two perpendicular directions result in transverse isotropic properties.

After hot pressing, selected regions of the composites were cut into cylinders, some with the axis along the compaction direction and others with the axis in a radial direction. These were used for thermal conductivity evaluations.

2.2. Thermal diffusivity measurements

Thermal diffusivity measurements were made using the flash technique (12). In this technique the front face of a disc shaped sample is subject to a short duration heat pulse and the temperature history of the opposite face recorded. In the UMIST facility (17) the heat pulse is supplied by a Nd glass laser ($\lambda = 1.06 \mu\text{m}$) of 0.6 ms pulse duration. The specimen was heated to the measurement temperature via a graphite susceptor located inside an induction coil. Radiation from the sample was collected and focussed on to a cooled InSb infra-red detector operating in the photovoltaic mode. The amplified signal from this detector was analysed by an IBM PC microcomputer. Specimens were thin discs ~8 mm diameter by 3 to 4 mm thick. Measurements were taken at 30–40°C temperature intervals during heating and cooling. Repeat temperature runs were carried out to ascertain whether any permanent changes had occurred. The thermal diffusivity of the carbon fibres were measured in a specially designed sample holder (7).

2.3 Specimen Characterisation

Densities of both the composites and the carbon fibre were measured using the displacement method. The composites specimens were weighed in air and in the liquid, iodoethane. The carbon fibres were weighed in air and ethanol.

Metallographic examination was carried out on all samples using a Sight Systems Image Manager. The volume fractions of carbon fibre were obtained from area counting of nine different areas of the sample surface. These were averaged to give the mean fibre volume fraction of each of the materials studied. The measured densities were used to determine the volume fraction of porosity which is given by

$$V_P = \frac{\rho_f V_f + \rho_m (1 - V_f) - \rho_c}{\rho_m} \quad (1)$$

where V_f is the volume fraction of fibre and ρ_f , ρ_m and ρ_c are the densities of carbon fibre, metal matrix and composite, respectively. The densities assumed for copper and aluminium were 893 and 270 kg m^{-3} , respectively.

3. RESULTS

The results for the fibre and porosity volume fraction are shown in Table 2. It is noteworthy that the Cu/Al specimens have higher porosity levels than the C/Cu samples and that this difference is especially pronounced at the 50% V_f level. Also of significance is the fact that volume fraction of porosity increases as the fraction of carbon fibres is increased. Thermal diffusivity data for the five C/Cu samples sectioned so that the specimen axis (direction of heat flow) was normal to the hot pressing direction are shown in figure 2.

Whilst these show a trend of decreasing thermal diffusivity with increasing V_f there is only a small difference between 0.1 and 0.2 V_f samples. Thermal diffusivity data for the C/Cu sample sectioned so that the specimen axis (direction of heat flow) was parallel to the hot pressing direction are shown in figure 3.

Fig. 2. Thermal diffusivity of C/Cu samples perpendicular to hot pressing direction. Key: ■ 0.1 C/Cu, □ 0.2 C/Cu, + 0.3 C/Cu, * 0.4 C/Cu, × 0.5 C/Cu.

TABLE 2. SPECIMEN CHARACTERISATION

Specimen	Nominal F.V.F.	Density kg m^{-3}	V_f %	V_p %
0.1 C/Cu	0.1	829	9.4	0.22
0.2 C/Cu	0.2	767	18.3	0.32
0.3 C/Cu	0.3	704	27.4	0.52
0.4 C/Cu	0.4	635	36.5	1.29
0.5 C/Cu	0.5	573	44.6	2.01
0.2 C/Al	0.2	260	15.5	0.72
0.3 C/Al	0.3	253	24.4	1.27
0.5 C/Al	0.5	217	50.4	9.33
Carbon Fibres	-	210	-	15.0

Fig. 3. Thermal diffusivity of C/Cu samples parallel to hot pressing direction. Key: ■ 0.1 C/Cu, □ 0.2 C/Cu, + 0.3 C/Cu, * 0.4 C/Cu, × 0.5 C/Cu.

Again these show the trend of decreasing thermal diffusivity with increasing V_f . For any given V_f the values are consistently lower than those cut normal to the hot pressing direction, and this is especially so for the two high V_f samples.

Fig. 4. Thermal diffusivity of C/Al sample perpendicular to hot pressure direction. Key: ■ 0.2 C/Al, □ 0.3 C/Al, + 0.5 C/Al.

The thermal diffusivities of the C/Al composites normal to the hot pressing direction are shown in figure 4. There is a relatively small difference between the 0.2 and 0.3 V_f but a very large decrease for the 0.5 V_f sample.

The thermal stability of these composites was investigated by carrying out repeat measurement runs. All the copper based composites are thermally stable, repeat runs producing no change in thermal diffusivity. This is shown in figure 5 for 0.5 C/Cu which would be expected to be the worst case.

Fig. 5. Effect of thermal cycling on the 0.5 C/Cu sample perpendicular to hot pressing direction. Key: ■ Run 1, □ Run 2, + Run 3.

In contrast the C/Al composites did not exhibit thermal stability during repeat cycling up to 500°C. This is exemplified in figure 6 for three measurement runs on the sample 0.3 V_f C/Al. A significant decrease of some 20% was noted after initially heating to 500°C and a smaller decrease noted after the second thermal cycle.

Fig. 6. Effect of thermal cycling on the thermal diffusivity of the 0.3 C/Al sample. Key: ■ Run 1, □ Run 2, + Run 3.

Thermal diffusivity (α_c) may be converted to thermal conductivity (λ_c) using equation 2.

$$\lambda_c = \alpha_c (V_f C_f \rho_f + V_m C_m \rho_m) \quad (2)$$

The specific heats are computed using fifth order polynomials. For graphite this polynomial is synthesised from measurements on POCO graphite from 300–1000K (18) and from 1500–3000K on a carbon/carbon fibre composite (19) and is given by

$$C_g \text{ (J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}\text{)} = 685.3 + 5.9199T - 5.5271 \times 10^{-3} T^2 + 2.6677 \times 10^{-6} T^3 - 6.4429 \times 10^{-10} T^4 + 6.1622 \times 10^{-14} T^5 \quad (3)$$

For copper and aluminium the specific heats are obtained from Touloukian (20) and are given by

$$C_{Cu} \text{ (J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}\text{)} = 494.1 - 0.67517 T + 1.5596 \times 10^{-3} T^2 - 1.3215 \times 10^{-6} T^3 + 3.2968 \times 10^{-10} T^4 + 7.9264 \times 10^{-14} T^5 \quad (4)$$

$$C_{Al} \text{ (J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}\text{)} = 1119.3 - 4.9494 T + 2.4922 \times 10^{-2} T^2 - 5.0259 \times 10^{-5} T^3 + 4.6562 \times 10^{-8} T^4 - 1.6178 \times 10^{-11} T^5 \quad (5)$$

Fig. 7. Thermal diffusivity and conductivity of EI20 carbon fibres. Diffusivity: ■ Heating, □ Cooling; Conductivity: + Heating, ☒ Cooling.

Fig. 8. Thermal conductivity of C/Cu perpendicular to hot pressing direction. Key: \square 0.1 C/Cu, \square 0.2 C/Cu, + 0.3 C/Cu, * 0.4 C/Cu, \square 0.5 C/Cu.

Fig. 9. Thermal conductivity of C/Cu parallel to hot pressing direction. Key: \square 0.1 C/Cu, \square 0.2 C/Cu, + 0.3 C/Cu, * 0.4 C/Cu, \square 0.5 C/Cu.

Fig. 10. Thermal conductivity of C/Al samples perpendicular to hot pressing direction. Key: \square 0.2 C/Al, \square 0.3 C/Al, + 0.5 C/Al.

Fig. 11. Micrograph of 0.2 C/Cu perpendicular to hot pressing direction.

Fig. 13. Micrograph of 0.2 C/Cu parallel to hot pressing direction.

Fig. 12. Micrograph of 0.5 C/Cu perpendicular to hot pressing direction.

Fig. 14. Micrograph of 0.5 C/Cu parallel to hot pressing direction.

The thermal diffusivity of carbon fibres and using C_f obtained from equation 3, their derived thermal conductivity are plotted in figure 7. These show that whereas the diffusivity decreases monotonically with increasing temperature the thermal conductivity exhibits a fairly broad peak at 250–500°C. Using equations 2–5 the measured data have been converted to thermal conductivity and are plotted in figures 8–10.

Micrographs from selected samples are shown in figures 11 and 12 for 0.2 C/Cu and 0.5 C/Cu samples normal to the hot pressing direction and in figures 13 and 14 for the 0.2 and 0.5 C/Cu samples parallel to the hot pressing direction. A number of observations may be made

a) It is clearly evident that perpendicular to the hot pressing direction, a majority but not all, of the chopped carbon fibres are oriented parallel to the specimen axis.

b) In figures 13 and 14, for the samples cut parallel to the pressing direction a majority of the fibres are oriented normal to the specimen axis.

c) For both orientations the porosity is clearly evident in the 0.5 V_f samples. This is a consequence of the high V_f and occurs at fibre cross over points or where there are regions of high fibre density.

4. DISCUSSION

It is desirable to be able to compare the observed behaviour with that expected on the basis of theoretical predictions. A number of mathematical models are available to predict the thermal conductivity of composites. These have been reviewed on a number of occasions (22,23) and the criteria for meaningful analysis have been itemised. It would perhaps be instructive to consider these and briefly discuss the extent to which our composites satisfy these criteria. Firstly, we should have available data for the pure matrix material preferably isotropic. Copper and aluminium are both isotropic and their thermal conductivities are well documented. The question of whether this has the same value as the composite matrix is largely unanswered since the material should have an identical microstructure. It is difficult to adjudicate whether any changes such as increased dislocation density will occur due to the presence of the reinforcements. Secondly, reliable measurement or estimation of the thermal conductivity of the reinforcement should be available. Here we have an immediate problem because the carbon fibres are anisotropic. Whilst the thermal conductivity parallel to the fibre axis has been determined, it is incorrect to assume these values transverse to the fibre axis. Thermal conductivity in graphite is strongly affected by the crystallite grain size (20,21). Whittaker et al (26) have deduced the transverse thermal conductivity of a PAN based carbon fibre from T.E.M. measurements of grain size (27) and deduced a value roughly constant at $\sim 12 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ for $T > 200^\circ\text{C}$. Whilst there is strong evidence (1,2) that the axial thermal conductivity of graphite fibres is enhanced as the final processing temperature is increased microstructural studies by a number of authors suggest that the transverse grain size of the carbon fibre is hardly affected by high temperature annealing (28,29). Hence a value of $12 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ is not unreasonable but this implies an anisotropy factor in thermal conductivity of 13–19 for the two orientations of the carbon fibre.

Two further factors that are usually assumed on most models are that the composite is an arrangement of two phases and, more importantly, that the interface between the two phases is perfect and presents no barrier to heat flow. As noted by Mottram and Taylor (6) these assumptions are almost certainly unlikely to be true. Because of differential thermal expansion, on cooling from the processing temperature some degree of delamination between fibre and matrix is likely to occur. Since a pore is a barrier to heat flow the presence and distribution of any porosity will have an important bearing on heat transfer. To that extent all composites should be considered ternary systems; fibre, matrix and porosity.

Hasselmann and Johnson (29) and Benveniste (30) calculated the effect that an interfacial contact resistance between fibre and matrix would have on the thermal conductivity. For the case of cylindrical inclusions oriented normal to the direction of heat flow Hasselmann and Johnson present an equation which includes an interfacial heat transfer coefficient h_c ($\text{W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$)

$$\lambda_c = \lambda_m \frac{\left[\left[\frac{\lambda_c}{\lambda_m} - 1 - \frac{\lambda_f}{rh_c} \right] V_f + \left[1 + \frac{\lambda_f}{rh_c} + \frac{\lambda_f}{\lambda_m} \right] \right]}{\left[\left[1 + \frac{\lambda_f}{rh_c} - \frac{\lambda_f}{\lambda_m} \right] V_f + \left[1 + \frac{\lambda_f}{rh_c} + \frac{\lambda_f}{\lambda_m} \right] \right]} \quad (6)$$

where λ is the radius of the fibre, V_f is the volume fraction of the fibre and the suffixes f, c, m refer to fibre matrix and composite, respectively. (If the conductivity of the interface h_c is very large equation 7 reduces to the Rayleigh equation (31).) This analysis has been used by Greenfield and Schulz to analyse the electrical conductivity of C/Al and C/Cu composites (32).

Parallel to the fibre axis a simple series equation is usually used (5,6,7,32)

$$\lambda_c = \lambda_f V_f + \lambda_m (1 - V_f - V_p) \quad (7)$$

If we apply this simple analysis given by equation 7 to the composite where the majority of fibres are oriented parallel to the direction of heat flow the predicted thermal conductivities are as given by figure 15. It can be clearly seen than predicted thermal

Fig. 15. Comparison of measured and predicted thermal conductivities for C/Cu samples cut perpendicular to hot pressing direction. Key: ■ 0.1 C/Cu, + 0.3 C/Cu, □ 0.5 C/Cu.

conductivities are much higher than the measured values. This implies one of two possibilities

- either the matrix thermal conductivity has a lower value than we have assumed,
- or
- there is a significant thermal barrier resistance at the interface between matrix and fibres at orientations other than parallel to the heat flow direction.

If we now consider the data for samples where the majority of fibres are oriented perpendicular to the heat flow direction then equation 6 represents one possible solution. The problem here is the difficulty of quantifying the interfacial heat transfer coefficient or adequately accounting for the total volume of porosity present. One of the earliest models due to Bruggemann (34) has been used by Whittaker et al (26) and Mottram and Taylor (6) to analyse heat flow perpendicular to fibre orientation in an orthogonally reinforced unidirectional carbon/carbon fibre composite. The Bruggemann variable dispersion equation may be stated

$$1 - V_D = \frac{\lambda_D - \lambda_c}{\lambda_D - \lambda_m} \left[\frac{\lambda_c}{\lambda_m} \right]^{\frac{1}{X+1}} \quad (8)$$

where V_D is the volume fraction of the dispersed phase, λ_D , λ_m , λ_c are the thermal conductivities of the discontinuous phase, matrix and composite respectively. X is a generalised shape factor for the discontinuous phase. In essence this equation is solved twice; firstly by letting V_D be porosity for which $\lambda_D = 0$, and secondly, by letting V_D be the volume fraction of fibres to compute either the thermal conductivity λ_c of the solid fraction of the composite, or matrix or fibre perpendicular conductivity (26).

However, it is difficult to apply this approach to predict the transverse thermal conductivity of the short fibre composite where the fibres have a spectrum of orientations. This has been gradually realised in recent years. Various analyses have been carried out which require some information on the microstructural geometry of the dispersed phase in order to specify closer bounds on predicted composite thermal conductivities. In order to do this it is necessary to specify the statistical distribution functions for the dispersed phase. For cylinders Torquato (35) derives upper and lower limits for fourth order bounds

$$\lambda_1 \leq \lambda_c \leq \lambda_u$$

$$\frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_m} = \frac{1 + V_2 \beta_{21} - (1-V_2) \xi_2 \beta_{21}^2}{1 - V_2 \beta_{21} - (1-V_2) \xi_2 \beta_{21}^2} \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\lambda_u}{\lambda_m} = \frac{\lambda_f}{\lambda_m} \left[\frac{1 + (1-V_2) \beta_{12} - V_2 (1-\xi_2) \beta_{12}^2}{1 + (1-V_2) \beta_{12} - V_2 (1-\xi_2) \beta_{12}^2} \right] \quad (10)$$

where

$$\beta_{21} = \frac{\lambda_f / \lambda_m - 1}{\lambda_f / \lambda_m + 1} \quad \text{and} \quad \beta_{12} = \frac{1 - \lambda_f / \lambda_m}{1 + \lambda_f / \lambda_m} \quad (11)$$

ξ_2 is the microstructural three point parameter which depends on the n -point correlation function which relate the probability that n -points thrown at random in the composite will all be in the same phase. The value of ξ_2 lies in the range $0 > \xi_2 < 1$ and has been evaluated for various geometries of dispersed phase; for equi-sized fully impenetrable cylinders (36) (which should apply to the present situation) periodic lattices of equi-sized cylinders (37) etc. Hatta and Taya (38) use Eshelby's (39) equivalent inclusion method to deduce expressions for the effect thermal conductivity of a short fibre composite. For a two dimensional situation where the random distribution of fibres is within a plane, λ_c is given by

$$\frac{\lambda_c}{\lambda_m} = 1 + \frac{V_f \left[\frac{\lambda_f}{\lambda_m} - 1 \right] \left[\left[\frac{\lambda_f}{\lambda_m} - 1 \right] (D_3 + D_1) + 2 \right]}{2 \left[\frac{\lambda_f}{\lambda_1} - 1 \right]^2 (1 - V_f) D_1 D_3 + \left[\frac{\lambda_f}{\lambda_m} - 1 \right] (2 - V_f) (D_1 + D_3) + 2} \quad (12)$$

where the D 's are the Depolarisation coefficients (40). For the specific case where the dispersed phase is rod or fibre shaped $D_1 = D_2 = \frac{1}{2}$, $D_3 = 0$.

These approaches have emphasised the need to carefully characterise the microstructure of composites. However they consider the composite to be a two phase mixture, whereas, in all real systems, porosity is present. It is sensible to assume that the bulk of the porosity exists as elongated ellipsoids aligned parallel to the fibre direction, and this will reduce the thermal conductivity. We have not carried out a sufficiently detailed microstructural

characterisation of the fibre distributions in these composites, and this will form the subject of a further paper.

REFERENCES

1. V.I. Volga, V. Frolov, and V. Usov, Inorg. Mat. **9**, 643 (1973).
2. J. Heremans, I. Rahim and M.S. Dresselhaus, Phys. Rev. B. **32**, 6742 (1985).
3. A. Kelly, Phil. Trans. Roy. Soc., **A322**, 409 (1987).
4. G.R. Sharp and T.A. Loflin, NASA Tech. Memo. 102434 (1990).
5. M. Pilling, B. Yates, M.A. Black and P. Tattersall, J. Mat. Sci. **14**, 1326 (1979).
6. J.T. Mottram and R. Taylor, Comp. Sci. and Tech., **29**, 189 (1987).
7. A.J. Whittaker, R. Taylor and H. Tawil, Proc. Roy. Soc., **A430**, 167 (1990).
8. D.P.H. Hasselmann, L.F. Johnson, R. Syed, M.P. Taylor and K. Chyung, J. Mat. Sci., **22**, 701 (1987).
9. H. Tawil, L.D. Bentsen and D.P.H. Hasselmann, Carbon, **22**(6), 57 (1984).
10. K. Kuniya, H. Arakawa, T. Kanani and A. China, Trans. Jap. Inst. Met., **28**, 819 (1987).
11. Y. Hinesawa, E. Takegoshi, S. Imura and F. Kiyoke, J. Soc. Mat. Sci. Japan, **35**, 1212 (1986).
12. W.J. Parker, R.J. Jenkins, C.P. Butler and G.L. Abbott, J. Appl. Phys., **32**, 1679 (1961).
13. R.V. Level, "Mechanical Fundamentals of Consolidation", Metals Handbook, 9th Ed., vol. 7, Powder Metallurgy (Metals Park, OH: ASM, 1986) 296.
14. S.G. Advani and C.L. Tucker, "The Use of Tensors to Describe and Predict Fiber Orientation in Short Fiber Composites," Jour. of Rheology, **31**(8), (1987), 751.
15. F.P. Folger and C.L. Tucker, Jour. of Reinf. Plast. Compos., **3** (1984) 98.
16. I.G. Greenfield, "Measurements of Physical Properties of Hot Pressed Graphite/Copper and Graphite/Aluminium Composites; Specimen Preparation," Metal and Ceramic matrix Composites: modelling and Mechanical Behaviour, (Warrendale, PA, TMS, 1990).
17. R. Taylor, J. Phys. E., Sci. Inst., **13**, 1193 (1980).
18. R.E. Taylor and H.E. Groot, High Temp.-High Press., **12**, 147 (1980).
19. A. Cezairliyan and A.P. Miller, Int. J. Thermophysics, **1**, 317 (1980).
20. Y.S. Touloukian, E.H. Buyco, "Thermophysical Properties of Solids - Vol.4, Specific Heats of Metallic Solids" Plenum, New York, (1970).
21. Y.S. Touloukian, R.W. Powell, C.Y. Ho, P.W. Klemens, "Thermophysical properties of solids Vol. 1, Thermal conductivity of metals and alloys", Plenum, New York, (1970).
22. R. Taylor, "Thermophysical properties of composites", to be published in Encyclopaedia of Composites, ed. S.M. Lee (1991).
23. J.T. Mottram and R. Taylor, "Thermal transport properties of composites, *ibid.*"
24. R. Taylor, K.E. Gilchrist and L.J. Poston, Carbon, **6**, 537 (1968).
25. B.T. Kelly and K.E. Gilchrist, Carbon, **7**, 355 (1969).
26. A.J. Whittaker and R. Taylor, Proc. Roy. Soc. **A480**, 199 (1990).
27. A.J. Whittaker, R. Taylor and H. Tawil, Proc. Roy. Soc. **A430**, 183 (1990).
28. D.J. Johnson, Phil. Trans. Roy. Soc. **A294**, 443 (1980).
29. D.P.H. Hasselmann and L.F. Johnson, J. Comp. Mat., **21**, 508 (1987).
30. Y. Benveniste, J. Appl. Phys., **61**, 2843 (1987).
31. Lord Rayleigh, Phil. Mag., **34**, 481 (1892).
32. I.G. Greenfield and M. Schulz, "Measurement of electrical resistivity of C/Cu and C/Al composites," Proc. 12th Ann. Discontinuously reinforced MMC Working group meeting 16-1 (MMC.AC Santa Barbara) July 1990.
33. J. Brennan, L.D. Bentsen and D.P.H. Hasselmann, J. Mat. Sci., **20**, 2339 (1982).
34. D.A.G. Bruggemann, Ann. der Physik, **24**, 636 (1935).
35. S. Torquato, Rev. in Chem. Eng., **4**, 151 (1987).
36. S. Torquato and F. Ledo, Proc. Roy. Soc., **A417**, 59 (1988).
37. R.C. McPhedron and G.W. Milton, Appl. Phys., **26**, 207 (1981).
38. H. Hatta and M. Taya, J. Appl. Phys. **58**, 2478 (1985).
39. J.D. Eshelby, Proc. Roy. Soc., **A241**, 376 (1951).
40. T. Mori and K. Tanaka, Acta Met., **23**, 571 (1973).